

Privacy protected crowd source map

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Problem:

Crowdsourced maps are a useful tool in addressing crisis situations. Used in humanitarian response for crisis situations such as Haiti and Nepal earthquakes, floods in India. There are ingrained issues with crowd source mapping related to protecting privacy, customization for addressing regional or case based responses[1]. Platform such as Ushahidi which are majorly used in crowd source mapping has, apart from the above issues, problems related with lack of Application programming interface, client side provision of data (for big data management) and customization interface.

Covid 19 pandemic situation gives unique problems in addressing the supply chain management and disease spread containment. The situations are alarmingly escalating which need the best of humanitarian response to address it. There is a need for a crowd source map, which has a strict privacy protection, such as removing location, personal details from crowd source map would be helpful in addressing. Assurance of privacy protection can make people report more about health conditions and daily requirements which can be helpful in identifying spread zones, managing supply chain of essentials.

Solution:

In crowd source mapping, there are two players, one is reporters and another is responders. Obscuring the point location of the reporter with noisy data is a solution to remove the location details from the crowd source map. One way of automating the noisy data generation is to relate randomly with public utilities nearby the reporter location. Road networks are the nearest point of public utilities for any human settlement. Developing a random point generation algorithm surrounding the reporter's point with road network surrounding could make the nearest noisy location to the person, within a buffer of 1-2km for Indian situations.

The personal details can be obscured by using encryption libraries for string and maninting it in pandas dataframe. Share the key with respective responders (authorities/volunteers/supply chain utilities) to use. Following lock and key model for the data published in the map. Providing a mechanism to give key from reporters to responders to know about the report. But having a dashboard of information about the report categories and its location visualization to general view.

In crowd source mapping the server side delivery of data is increasingly observed as laggy and complex to operate in large data management such as above >50,000 reports, such in ushahidi

and Google map. The Kepler <https://kepler.gl/>, provides a solution to this by having a client side data processing and visualization facility for web mapping.

Along with this, having a static web page based site could organize the components (noisy location generation, Pandas dataframe column encryption, Kepler.gl for visualization). Static web page would reduce the lag and simplify the content delivery.

Notes:

As a software provider, this solution would make one to act as a mere digital infrastructure provider. Completely moves the content responsibility to major two players(reporters and responders) of crowd source mapping exercise in a community. Ensuring the privacy and protection of data is vested onto software providers.

Moreover this model can be extended further to use it in non crisis situations into essential marketplace development, such as transportation services where it works as an alternative decentralized model to the current centralized car pooling services.

Risks and failure points

Protection and encryption of data is one of most important aspect of this services and failure in that aspect is detrimental to the model

Failure in adequate communication and localization about the application is also a risk factor to consider which can block its wide adoption

References and tools

1. Hunt, A., Specht, D. Crowdsourced mapping in crisis zones: collaboration, organisation and impact. *Int J Humanitarian Action* 4, 1 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41018-018-0048-1>, <https://jhumanitarianaction.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s41018-018-0048-1>
2. Note on encrypting csv files, <https://stackoverflow.com/questions/52116171/how-to-encrypt-and-decrypt-pandas-dataframe-with-decryption-key>
3. Encryption of certain columns in pandas https://github.com/bennywij/junk-drawer/blob/master/secret_pandas.py